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Assessing the Distribution of PAHs in Water and Sediment of Selected Oil-Producing Communities in Delta South Senatorial District, Delta State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

To enhance the understanding of the distribution of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) compounds and their immediate ecological risks from crude oil pollution, this research work examined the concentrations, distribution patterns, and ecological risks of PAHs in soil and water polluted by crude oil in sediment and water samples collected from 8 locations (BAT, BOB, KOK, OKE, OLO, ORE, TSE, and UZE), in the Delta State, Southern region in Nigeria. The PAH distribution in the sediments from the 8 locations reveals the presence of benzo[b]fluoranthene as the dominant PAH type with a concentration of up to 4.03 µg/L, which was closely followed by acenaphthylene and benzo[k]fluoranthene with concentrations corresponding to 2.33 µg/L and 2.14 µg/L, respectively. The distribution of various PAH concentrations in different water samples indicates that PAH types Benzo(a)pyrene and Benz(a)anthracene were present in the highest concentrations, 0.57 µg/L and 0.53 µg/L, in the water sample from location BAT. The findings established that sediment from BAT was most contaminated with PAHs, while sediment from TSE was the least contaminated with PAHs. However, the findings from water analysis proved that across all 8 locations under investigation, the water sample collected from KOK is the most contaminated with the various PAH types, with a cumulative PAH concentration of 4.51 µg/L, and ranking 1st in PAH contamination levels, corresponding to a 16.2% in the percentage PAHs spatial distribution.

Keywords: Delta South Senatorial District, Poly Aromatic Hydrocarbons, sediments, Water

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons, also known as PAHs, are a group of organic compounds, which are chiefly colourless, but which sometimes assume a whitish or straw colour. They are very common and may be derived from either natural or anthropogenic sources (Okedere, O. B., & Elehinafe, F. B. 2022). PAHs occurs naturally from various sources such as open burning, escape from petroleum or coal deposit, and volcanic eruptions. Other anthropogenic or man-made sources of PAHs may be pyrolytic or incomplete combustion of organic substances. Consequently, processes such as the treatment of tar sands, crude fractions, bituminous coal, and the use of the refined petroleum products, which constitute the main anthropogenic sources of PAHs (Emoyan *et al.*, 2020). Other anthropogenic Sources include the burning of municipal and medical wastes, vegetative waste products, and biomass materials in general (Nduka, *et al.*, 2025).

The Niger Delta area of Nigeria harbours many anthropogenic sources of polluting organic PAH compounds, and the exploration of crude oil is believed to be mainly responsible for most of these polluting agents (Saunders *et al.*, 2022). The Niger Delta, however, lends itself very easily to various sources of the product of the land and adjacent sea, having been and in a very high degree contaminated by large exports and imports of crude oil and petroleum products (Faboya *et al.*, 2023). Ivwurie & Okorodudu (2021) carried out an investigation on the sources, both primary (pure hydrocarbons) and secondary (soils), of petroleum hydrocarbons (PAHs) in certain locations in Ughelli and its neighbourhood in Delta State of Nigeria, which appeared to be polluted with hydrocarbons. It was found that the most important constituents of soil PAHs in these cases were the lower homologues (2-3 rings) and the non-carcinogenic hydrocarbons. Similarly, the temporal and spatial distribution of various PAHs in soils and the assessment of human health hazards have been investigated (Emoyan, *et al.*, 2022) The findings revealed significant variation in the concentration of PAHs, indicating a possible risk of exposure for ecosystems and mankind. The molecular weight distribution, percentage composition, and possible sources of pollution of PAHs have been studied. (Okoye *et al.*, 2023). The presence of high molecular weight PAHs along some specific diagnostic ratios indicating that the pollution is from both petrogenic and pyrogenic sources is outlined (Umudi *et al.*, 2025). In some sites of the Niger Delta, the Risk quotient values exceeded 800, which indicated that remediation is warranted in such areas to avert adverse effects on environmental health. To enhance its understanding of the distribution of various PAHs and their immediate ecological risks from crude oil pollution, this research work examined the distribution patterns, concentration levels, and ecological risks of PAHs in soil and water polluted by crude oil. The research work is limited to eight communities in the Delta South Senatorial District of Nigeria, drawn from four Local Government Areas out of the eight in the State. The table below identify the community chosen for the study

TABLE 1.0: Community And Their Local Government Area

COMMUNITIES	INDIGENOUS TRIBE	LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA
Bateren	Itsekiri	Warri North
Bobi	Itsekiri	Warri South West
Kokodiagbene	Ijaw	Warri North
Okerenkoko	Ijaw	Warri south west
Olomoro	Isoko	Isoko South
Orere	Itsekiri	Warri South West
Tsekelewi	Ijaw	Warri North
Uzere	Isoko	Isoko South

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this research, the analytical test method for polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), based on USEPA method 8270, was conducted using high-quality reagents. The reagents included analytical-grade dichloromethane (DCM, HPLC grade) sourced from Fisher Scientific in Loughborough, UK. Anhydrous sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4), powdered silica gel (60-120 mesh), and acetone were obtained from BDH Laboratory Supplies in Poole, England. Additionally, the PAH reference standard mix (2000 ppm), which includes sixteen different PAHs, was acquired from Accu Standard Inc. in New Haven, USA.

2.1 Sample Collection and Preparation for PAH Analysis

Randomly selected portions of water and sediment samples used for the analysis were collected from three (3) Ijaw communities; Tsekelewu (TSE), Okenrenkoko (OKE), and Kokodiagbene (KOK), three Itsekiri communities; Orere (ORE), Bobi (BOB) and Bateren (BAT) and two Isoko communities; Olomoro (OLO) and Uzere (UZE). The sediment samples were grounded and mixed into fine particles using a ceramic mortar and pestle, ensuring uniformity. The homogenized sample was combined with anhydrous sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) to effectively absorb moisture in a ratio is 1:3 of sample to anhydrous sodium sulphate (Na_2SO_4) (USEPA, 2014).

2.1.1 Ultrasonic Extraction (Solid-Liquid Extraction method)

A known amount of finely ground, thoroughly mixed sediment (10g) was weighed into a clean extraction vessel using an electronic analytical balance (S-Mettler; FA210A model, USA). (USEPA,2014). Thirty milliliters of a dichloromethane and acetone (in the ratio 1:1 v/v) solvent mixture was added to the vessel containing the sediment sample. The mixture was sonicated for 15–30 minutes and then filtered. The supernatant was collected in a clean 100-mL beaker. This extraction process was replicated three times to optimize recovery, and the three supernatants were combined (USEPA,2014).

A procedural blank using dichloromethane (DCM) was also processed using the same extraction procedure as part of the Quality Control and Quality Assurance (QA/QC) measures (USEPA,2014).

2.1.3 Silica Gel Cleanup of Extracts

To ensure accurate PAH analysis, which can be tricky due to their low concentrations and the presence of interfering substances, a thorough clean-up step is essential. We prepared a glass column by packing it with glass wool, silica gel (to remove polar interferences), and anhydrous sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4). The column was then conditioned with dichloromethane (DCM). Furthermore, the combined extract was carefully transferred into the prepared column. PAHs were then eluted using 20 ml of DCM. The resulting eluate was then collected in a clean 50 ml glass beaker and prepared using a rotary evaporator-MSD Analysis for PAH concentrations. (USEPA, 2007).

2.2 GC-MSD Analysis for PAH concentrations

The analyte was separated and detected using an Agilent 6890 gas chromatograph and Agilent 5973N mass selective detector (GC-MSD). The PAH eluate was concentrated using a rotary evaporator (Searchtech instrument, RE52-2 model, USA) until its volume was reduced to about 1–2 mL. The concentrated eluate was transferred to a clean 2 mL Teflon screw-cap vial, tightly capped, labeled, and stored to prevent oxidation before GC-MSD analysis. GC-MS analysis determined PAH concentrations using an Agilent 6890 gas chromatograph and Agilent 5973N Mass Selective Detector (GC-MSD) from Agilent Technology, Palo Alto, CA, USA. The set-up consisted of an Agilent 19091J-413 - HP-5 Capillary column with specification (0.25 mm I.D \times 30 m \times 0.25 μm film thickness), composed of carrier gas (helium purity $\geq 99.999\%$) operated at constant flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The injection was slit less, with an injection volume (1 μL). The source temperature of the MS ion was 230 $^\circ\text{C}$, with an injection temperature and pressure of 50 $^\circ\text{C}$, and 13 psi. The full scan acquisition mode covered a mass range of 50–500 amu, with a 2.00 min purge time, a total flow of 23 mL/min, and a solvent delay of 3.5 min. A 1 μL aliquot of the extracted sample was injected into the GC-MSD. PAHs were identified by their retention times, with those having shorter retention times eluting first. PAH standard solutions were run under the same chromatographic conditions, and mean peak areas were plotted against concentrations to create calibration curves for the 16 priority PAH compounds. Procedural blanks were included for each sample batch to account for sample preparation and determination steps. Duplicate analyses were performed for every 10 to 20 batches of samples.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Physicochemical analysis of the Water Samples

The physicochemical analysis of the water samples from 8 locations coded as BAT, BOB, KOK, OKE, OLO, ORE, TSE, and UZE in the Delta State, Southern region in Nigeria are presented in Table 2.0. below.

Table 2.0: Characteristics of the Water samples from various location under investigation

Parameters	Test Method	BAT	BOB	KOK	OKE	OLO	ORE	TSE	UZE
pH	APHA 4500-H ⁺	7.70	6.60	5.60	5.00	5.70	7.10	6.50	5.20
Conductivity ($\mu\text{S/cm}$)	APHA 2510B	340	160	40	44	400	150	60	51
Salinity (ppt)	APHA 2520B	0.18	0.08	0.02	0.02	0.23	0.08	0.03	0.03
DO (mg/L)	APHA 4500-O-G	6.2	6.3	6.3	6.4	5.8	6.4	6.2	6.2
Turbidity (NTU)	APHA 2130B	1.34	2.09	0.83	0.75	4.50	0.90	1.36	1.44

The results proved that the pH of the water samples from KOK (5.60), OLO (5.70), and UZE (5.20) locations was acidic. The outcome indicates significant implications for the concentration, mobility, and persistence of contaminants in these water samples (Ovuoraye et al., 2021; Chinenye et al., 2022). Additionally, the highly acidic pH signifies reduced microbial degradation and enhanced adsorption of contaminants to sediments in these locations (Naz et al., 2022; Aryal, M. 2024). The water sample from UZE is the most acidic, with higher contaminant retention and the lowest microbial degradation. The pH of water samples from KOK, OLO, and UZE was significantly low, and did not satisfy the WHO pH (6-8) stipulated for clear water (Zheng et al., 2006; Naz et al., 2022). The pH of water samples from ORE (7.10) and BAT (7.70) lies within the range of neutral water. The outcome proved samples from ORE and BAT satisfied the WHO pH range (6-8), suggesting a balance in the degree of alkalinity and acidity of the medium, indicating a lower tendency of persistence of contamination, and improved detoxification. However, the pH of samples from BOB (6.60) and TSE (6.50) were close to neutral (7.0) and fell within the WHO range of pH (6-8), indicating a less acidic contamination level. In terms of conductivity of the water samples across all 8 locations, the sample from OLO has the highest electrical conductivity of 400 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, followed by the sample from BAT (340 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). Other locations BOB (160 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), and ORE (150 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) recorded moderate conductivity, while samples from UZE, KOK, TSE, and OKE recorded conductivity $\leq 60 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

The degree of salinity of the water samples varies significantly, with higher values corresponding to 0.23 ppt recorded in the OLO location, which was closely followed by 0.18 ppt found at the BAT location. Salinity of water samples from BOB and ORE was equal to 0.08 ppt. The higher the salinity, the lower the tendency for bioavailability of contaminants, influencing partitioning between water and sediments. However, the degree of salinity in samples from locations KOK, OKE, TSE, and UZE was relatively low ≤ 0.03 ppt. In terms of dissolved oxygen content (DO), it is essential for aerobic microbial degradation of contaminants in water samples. Low DO values slow down the breakdown of contaminants, increasing persistence (Bozorg-Haddad et al., 2021). The DO values of the water samples lie between 5.8 and 6.4, indicating there are no significant variations in the DO levels of water across all samples, irrespective of location.

Turbidity is a clear indicator of the presence of suspended particles that can adsorb PAHs, affecting their transport and concentration (Rugner et al., 2013). In terms of contamination levels, the turbidity of the samples are BAT (1.34 NTU), BOB (2.09 NTU), KOK (0.83 NTU), OLO (4.50 NTU), OKE (0.75 NTU), ORE (0.90 NTU), TSE (1.36 NTU), and UZE (1.44 NTU). The turbidity of the samples from the various locations under investigation was relatively $< 5\text{NTU}$, suggesting the samples satisfied the WHO standard for clear water (Ovuoraye et al., 2021; 2022). Although turbidity of 4.5 NTU was detected in OLO, and 2.09 NTU in BOB, these are clear indications of some level of total solids contamination in the water sample (Ugonabo et al., 2022). This outcome suggests possible contaminant accumulation with partial microbial access due to the mild turbidity in samples (Ovuoraye et al., 2021; 2022).

3.2 Physicochemical Properties of the Sediments

The pH variation across the soil samples collected across the various locations is presented in Table 3.0. The results proved that the pH of the sediments was predominantly acidic, irrespective of location. The pH of sediments from BAT (5.05), KOK (5.02), UZE (5.12), and TSE (5.84) was less than 6.0, indicating signals that signify reduced microbial degradation, a high degree of persistence, and enhanced adsorption of contaminants to sediments in these locations. The pH of sediments from ORE (6.15), OLO (6.10), and OKE (6.50), although less acidic, can also affect microbial degradation, solubility, and adsorption. Acidic pH slows biodegradation and increases PAH persistence (Hu et al., 2025).

Table 3.0: Physicochemical properties of the Sediment samples from different locations

Parameters	Test Method	BAT	BOB	KOK	OKE	OLO	ORE	TSE	UZE
pH	APHA 4500-H ⁺	5.05	4.93	5.02	6.50	6.10	6.15	5.84	5.12
Conductivity (µS/cm)	APHA 2510B	1320	2944	64	104	36	1264	52	68

The summary of the PAH contaminant distributed in the Water and Sediments samples collected across all eight locations under investigation are presented in Table 4a, 4b, 5a and 5b. The outcome in Table 4a and 4b proved that PAH type naphthalene was predominantly absent across 8 locations. In contrast, of all the PAH contaminant types under investigation, benzo[b]fluoranthene, although relatively absent in samples collected from OKE and OLO locations, was significantly present in water samples collected from the other 6 locations under investigation. The results in Table 4a and 4b confirmed that the principal PAH contaminant in the water across all location under investigation was benzo[b]fluoranthene, with a maximum 1.34 µg/L in water from the KOK location, and a cumulative concentration of 3.34 µg/L.

The result in Table 5a and 5b shows the concentration of PAHs obtained from the sediment samples in the 8 locations. A close observation reveals that Benzo[b]fluoranthene has the densest accumulation of 16.23 mg/kg

TABLE 4a: PAHs Concentration in Water samples from locations BAT, BOB, KOK and OKE

Parameters	Test Method	BAT-W	BOB-W	KOK-W	OKE-W	Cumulative total
PAH Accumulation (µg/L)						
Naphthalene (NaPH)	USEPA 8270	B.D.	B.D.	B.D.	B.D.	--
Acenaphthylene (AceNaphty)		0.38	0.03	0.38	0.29	1.08
Acenaphthene (AceNaphthe)		B.D.	0.22	0.01	B.D.	0.23
Fluorene (Fluoren)		0.47	B.D.	B.D.	0.19	0.66
Phenanthrene (Phena)		B.D.	0.52	0.25	0.20	0.97
Anthracene (Anthra)		0.28	B.D.	B.D.	0.71	0.99
Fluoranthene (Fluoran)		0.51	0.11	0.51	0.48	1.61
Pyrene (Pyren)		0.34	B.D.	0.34	B.D.	0.68
Benz[a]anthracene (Benz A)		0.57	0.74	B.D.	0.38	1.69
Chrysene (Chry)		B.D.	0.42	0.46	0.16	1.04
Benzo[b]fluoranthene (B(b)flu)		0.34	0.26	1.34	B.D.	1.94
Benzo[k]fluoranthene (B(k)flu)		0.11	0.46	0.71	0.50	1.84
Benzo[a]pyrene (B(a)P)		0.53	0.45	B.D.	0.17	1.15
Indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene (Ind[123]Py)		0.26	B.D.	B.D.	B.D.	0.26
Dibenz[a,h,]anthracene (Dib[a,h]An)		0.35	0.25	0.35	0.48	1.43
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene (B[ghi]P)		0.16	0.68	0.16	0.20	1.20
Sum of PAH (µg/L)		4.30	4.14	4.51	3.76	16.71

TABLE 4b: PAHs Concentration in Water samples from locations OLO, ORE, TSE and UZE

Parameters	Test Method	OLO-W	ORE-W	TSE-W	UZE-W	Cumulative total
PAH Accumulation (µg/L)						
Naphthalene (NaPH)	USEPA 8270	B.D.	B.D.	B.D.	B.D.	--
Acenaphthylene (AceNaphty)		0.76	0.17	B.D.	0.20	1.13
Acenaphthene (AceNaphthe)		0.19	0.16	0.18	0.62	1.15
Fluorene (Fluoren)		0.06	0.32	0.39	0.31	1.08
Phenanthrene (Phena)		B.D.	B.D.	0.41	B.D.	0.41
Anthracene (Anthra)		B.D.	B.D.	B.D.	0.19	0.19
Fluoranthene (Fluoran)		0.53	0.22	0.33	0.33	1.41
Pyrene (Pyren)		0.38	0.41	0.29	0.29	1.37
Benz[a]anthracene (Benz A)		B.D.	B.D.	B.D.	0.32	0.32
Chrysene (Chry)		B.D.	0.14	0.37	B.D.	0.51
Benzo[b]fluoranthene (B(b)flu)		B.D.	0.42	0.49	0.49	1.40
Benzo[k]fluoranthene (B(k)flu)		0.47	0.67	B.D.	0.35	1.49
Benzo[a]pyrene (B(a)P)		0.49	0.12	B.D.	0.12	0.73
Indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene (Ind[123]Py)		0.18	B.D.	0.14	0.14	0.46
Dibenz[a,h,]anthracene (Dib[a,h]An)		B.D.	0.36	0.41	0.41	1.18
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene (B[ghi]P)		B.D.	0.16	0.77	0.57	1.50
Sum of PAH (µg/L)		3.06	3.15	3.78	4.34	14.33

NOTE: BD= Below detection level (Not detected)

TABLE 5a: PAHs Concentration in Sediment samples from locations BAT, BOB, KOK and OKE

Parameters	Test Method	BAT-S	BOB-S	KOK-S	OKE-S	Cumulative total
PAH Accumulation (mg/kg)						
Naphthalene (NaPH)	USEPA 8270	0.76	1.17	0.76	1.92	3.45
Acenaphthylene (AceNaphty)		1.15	2.20	1.15	0.78	5.28
Acenaphthene (AceNaphthe)		2.33	0.16	2.33	1.04	5.86
Fluorene (Fluoren)		1.40	1.39	1.40	0.57	4.76
Phenanthrene (Phena)		0.76	0.55	0.76	0.84	2.91
Anthracene (Anthra)		0.83	1.91	0.83	0.13	3.70
Fluoranthene (Fluoran)		1.53	0.13	1.53	0.75	3.94
Pyrene (Pyren)		1.03	0.42	1.03	1.82	4.30
Benz[a]anthracene (Benz A)		1.70	1.11	0.70	1.15	4.66
Chrysene (Chry)		0.37	0.27	1.37	3.39	5.40
Benzo[b]fluoranthene (B(b)flu)		4.02	3.78	4.02	0.16	11.98
Benzo[k]fluoranthene (B(k)flu)		2.14	1.47	0.14	1.51	5.26
Benzo[a]pyrene (B(a)P)		1.60	0.35	0.60	2.30	4.85
Indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene (Ind[123]Py)		0.77	0.81	0.77	0.51	2.86
Dibenz[a,h,]anthracene (Dib[a,h]An)		1.04	0.74	1.04	1.44	4.26
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene (B[ghi]P)		0.49	2.03	0.49	0.60	3.61
Sum of PAH (mg/kg)		21.16	17.32	18.16	16.99	73.63

TABLE 5b: PAHs Concentration in Sediment samples from locations OLO, ORE, TSE and UZE

Parameters	Test Method	OLO-S	ORE-S	TSE-S	UZE-S	Cumulative total
PAH Accumulation (mg/kg)						
Naphthalene (NaPH)	USEPA 8270	0.01	0.29	0.12	0.92	1.34
Acenaphthylene (AceNaphty)		0.29	1.02	1.32	1.19	3.82
Acenaphthene (AceNaphthe)		0.16	1.68	0.32	0.04	2.20
Fluorene (Fluoren)		0.19	0.96	0.46	0.16	1.77
Phenanthrene (Phena)		1.03	0.96	0.23	1.23	3.45
Anthracene (Anthra)		1.70	1.84	1.46	0.46	5.46
Fluoranthene (Fluoran)		0.58	0.66	0.98	0.98	3.2
Pyrene (Pyren)		1.15	1.24	1.17	0.17	3.73
Benzo[a]anthracene (Benz A)		0.71	1.13	0.97	0.97	3.78
Chrysene (Chry)		0.59	0.31	0.10	0.10	1.10
Benzo[b]fluoranthene (B(b)flu)		1.36	0.27	1.16	1.46	4.25
Benzo[k]fluoranthene (B(k)flu)		1.70	1.01	1.25	1.65	5.61
Benzo[a]pyrene (B(a)P)		1.48	1.32	0.03	1.15	3.98
Indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene (Ind[123]Py)		0.15	0.71	0.43	0.43	1.72
Dibenz[a,h]anthracene (Dib[a,h]An)		1.87	1.17	0.22	0.22	3.48
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene (B[ghi]P)		0.31	0.48	0.11	0.41	1.31
Sum of PAH (mg/kg)		13.27	14.76	10.21	10.62	48.86

3.3 Spatial Distribution of PAH Types in Sediment Samples across Locations in Delta State

Figure 1(a-h) shows the spatial distribution of the selected PAH type in sediment samples collected from the 8 locations (BAT, BOB, KOK, OKE, OLO, ORE, TSE, and UZE), all in the Delta State, Southern region in Nigeria. The findings from 1(a) in Figure 1 proved that in location 1 (BAT), the presence of benzo[b]fluoranthene is the dominant PAH type with a concentration of 4.03 µg/L. This was closely followed by acenaphthylene and benzo[k]fluoranthene with concentrations corresponding to 2.33 µg/L and 2.14 µg/L, respectively. Other PAH types, including benzo(a)pyrene, benzo(a)anthracene, dibenz[a,h]anthracene, and fluorene, were present in moderate concentrations of < 2 µg/L. The PAHs least present in the sediment sample were chrysene and benzo[ghi]perylene in low concentrations of 0.37 µg/L and 0.49 µg/L respectively. A similar trend can be observed in 1(b) in Figure 1. The sediment in location 2 (BOB) was mostly contaminated with benzo[b]fluoranthene (3.78µg/L), acenaphthene (2.20µg/L), and Benzo[ghi]perylene (2.03 µg/L). Benzo(a)anthracene, anthracene, naphthalene, fluorene, and benzo(k)fluoranthene were, however, in moderate concentrations of < 2 µg/L, while other PAH types including chrysene, benzo(a)pyrene, fluoranthene, acenaphthene, and dibenz[a,h]anthracene were present in the sediment in low concentrations < 0.5 µg/L.

In 1(c) in Figure 1, the PAHs spatial distribution trend observed in location 3 (KOK) indicates that the sediment sample was mostly contaminated by benzo[b]fluoranthene (4.02 µg/L), and acenaphthylene (2.3 µg/L) was next. Only a slight disparity in terms of the concentrations of the PAHs present in the sediments can be observed. However, in contrast to the PAHs distribution in location 1, the concentrations of chrysene, pyrene, acenaphthalene, dibenz[a,h]anthracene, and fluorene in location 3 where significantly present in concentrations of < 1.50 µg/L, while the PAH type present in the lowest concentration in the sediment is benzo(k)fluoranthene, benzo[a]pyrene, and benzo(a)anthracene ranging from 0.14 µg/L to 0.7 µg/L

In contrast to the spatial distribution of PAHs in sediment samples from locations 1 to 3, the distribution results recorded for the sediment in location 4 (OKE) proved that chrysene and benzo(a)pyrene were majorly present in high concentrations, amounting to 3.39 µg/L and 2.30 µg/L, respectively. The concentrations of

PAH type naphthalene, benzo(a)anthracene, benzo(k)fluoranthene, and acenaphthylene were significantly $\leq 1.98 \mu\text{g/L}$. The PAHs with the lowest concentrations in the sediments were naphthalene and benzo[b]fluoranthene. The results for location 5 (OLO) shows that naphthalene ($2.03 \mu\text{g/L}$) and phenanthrene ($1.72 \mu\text{g/L}$) were the dominant PAH types present in the sediment. The accumulations of fluorene, anthracene, acenaphthylene, and benzo(a)pyrene were significantly less than $1.5 \mu\text{g/L}$, while acenaphthene and chrysene were present in the lowest concentrations of $0.18 \mu\text{g/L}$ and $0.39 \mu\text{g/L}$, respectively. For samples in location 6 (ORE), the results in 1(f) in Figure 1, anthracene ($1.84 \mu\text{g/L}$) and acenaphthene ($1.68 \mu\text{g/L}$) were dominant PAHs in the sediment sample. The concentrations of other PAH types, including benzo(k)fluoranthene, pyrene, benzo(a)pyrene, benzo(a)anthracene, and acenaphthylene, were present in $\leq 1.4 \mu\text{g/L}$, while benzo[b]fluoranthene and naphthalene were present in the smallest accumulations corresponding to $0.27 \mu\text{g/L}$, and $0.29 \mu\text{g/L}$, respectively.

However, the findings from the outline of the bar-chart in 1(g) of Figure 1, the concentrations of the dominant translate to anthracene ($1.46 \mu\text{g/L}$) and acenaphthylene ($1.32 \mu\text{g/L}$). The accumulations of pyrene, benzo(k)fluoranthene, fluoranthene, and benzo[b]fluoranthene were relatively $\leq 1.17 \mu\text{g/L}$, while the concentrations of chrysene, phenanthrene, benzo(a)pyrene, and dibenz[a,h]anthracene were less than $0.5 \mu\text{g/L}$. The least concentration present in the sediment was $0.03 \mu\text{g/L}$ recorded for benzo(a)pyrene. The outcome of the spatial distribution of the PAHs in location 8 (UZE) in Figure 1(h) confirmed that benzo[b]fluoranthene ($1.65 \mu\text{g/L}$) and benzo(k)fluoranthene ($1.65 \mu\text{g/L}$) were dominant PAHs in the sediment. Other PAHs including acenaphthylene, phenanthrene, and benzo(a)pyrene were present in concentrations $\leq 1.19 \mu\text{g/L}$. However, the PAH with the least concentration in the sediment from the UZE location is acenaphthalene, present in trace amounts corresponding to $0.04 \mu\text{g/L}$.

3.4 Distribution of PAH types in Water Samples across Locations in Delta State

Figure 2 (a – h), show the PAH distribution in the Water samples from the 8 locations.

The outlines of the bar graphs across Figure 2(a-h) indicate the distribution of various PAH concentrations in different water samples collected from the various locations in Delta State. The outline of 2(a) in Figure 2 showed that PAH type Benz(a)anthracene, and Benzo(a)pyrene were present in the highest concentrations, $0.57 \mu\text{g/L}$ and $0.53 \mu\text{g/L}$ in the water sample from location BAT. In location 2 (BOB), the PAH types benz(a)anthracene and benzo[ghi]perylene concentrations in the water corresponding to $0.74 \mu\text{g/L}$ and $0.68 \mu\text{g/L}$, respectively, can be observed in 2(b) in Fig. 2. This outcome established that PAH type benz(a)anthracene dominates the water with a higher concentration. In (KOK) location 3, PAH types benzo[b]fluoranthene, and benzo[k]fluoranthene were mostly present in higher values amounting to $1.34 \mu\text{g/L}$ and $0.71 \mu\text{g/L}$ respectively, while the water sample collected from (OKE) location 4, anthracene and benzo[k]fluoranthene were mostly present in higher concentrations of $0.71 \mu\text{g/L}$, and $0.51 \mu\text{g/L}$ as can be observed in the bar charts in Figure 2 (c-d). In location 5 (OLO), the PAH types naphthalene and benzo[ghi]perylene present in the water samples were recorded in higher concentrations of $0.18 \mu\text{g/L}$ and $0.16 \mu\text{g/L}$. The water samples from locations 6 (ORE) is mostly contaminated by higher concentrations of benzo[b]fluoranthene ($0.67 \mu\text{g/L}$), and benzo[k]fluoranthene ($0.42 \mu\text{g/L}$), while higher accumulations of benzo[ghi]perylene ($0.77 \mu\text{g/L}$), and benzo[b]fluoranthene ($0.49 \mu\text{g/L}$), were found in the water sample in location 7(TSE). In location 8 (UZE), the major PAH types discovered in the water sample were predominantly acenaphthylene present in $0.62 \mu\text{g/L}$ and benzo[ghi]perylene in $0.57 \mu\text{g/L}$.

(a)

(b)

(e)

(f)

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: Variation of the concentrations of different PAH types in Water samples across various locations

The outline **Figure 3(a-b)** shows the cumulative percentage of PAHs concentrations present in sediments and water samples across all locations 1-8, coded BAT, BOB, KOK, OKE, OLO, ORE, TSE, and UZE, respectively. The results in Figure 3(a) showed that sediments from the BAT and OLO locations were most contaminated with PAHs, amounting to 18% of the cumulative concentrations. The cumulative concentrations translate to 21.93 µg/L and 21.57 µg/L. ORE and OKE locations both have a cumulative PAH concentration of 12% each, which translates to 15.06 µg/L and 14.60 µg/L. The output from TSE and UZE confirmed a cumulative concentration of 10.33 µg/L and 14.54 µg/L, respectively. The findings established that sediment from BAT was most contaminated with PAHs, while sediment from TSE was the least contaminated with PAHs.

However, the findings from Figure 3(b) proved that across all 8 locations under investigation, the water sample collected from KOK (location 4) is the most contaminated with the various PAH types, with a cumulative concentration of 4.51 µg/L, and ranking 1st in PAH contamination levels, corresponding to a 16.2% in the percentage PAHs spatial distribution. This was closely followed by UZE with a cumulative PAH accumulation amounting to 4.43 µg/L corresponding to approximately 16% of the distribution.

From Figure 3(b) BAT and BOB showed the 3rd and 4th highest PAH levels, 15% and 14%. These outcomes translate to cumulative PAHs concentrations of 4.3 µg/L and 4.14 µg/L, respectively, in the water samples from the areas. The water samples in locations TSE and OKE ranked 5th and 6th in spatial distribution of the various PAH types, corresponding to in the 13.17% and 13.10% degree of contamination, which transcends to a cumulative concentration of 3.76 µg/L and 3.7 µg/L respectively, these were closely followed by the water sample from ORE location ranking 7th with a distribution of 10% and cumulative concentration of 3.15 µg/L. OLO locations ranked the least contaminated with PAHs, with a cumulative concentration of 0.63 µg/L and translating to only 2% degree of contamination.

Figure 3(a): Percentage distribution of PAHs sediment Sample in terms of Cumulative concentrations across different locations under investigation

Figure 3(b): Percentage distribution of PAHs Water sample in terms of Cumulative concentrations across different locations under investigation

The presence of some PAHs in samples collected from locations 1-8 but absence in other locations is probably due to the facts that the locations have different sources and exposures. Water samples containing PAH types such as likely came from a location with a significant source, such as proximity to a landfill, coal tar or crude oil sources, or indoor use of repellents, while samples from location 4, 7, and 8 has a much lower or non-existent source.

Additionally, the variation in physio chemical properties such as turbidity and DO contents of the water and sediment samples across different locations confirmed the variations in biodegradability index, bioaccumulation, and probable affects the partial distributions of PAH types in these locations.

This can account for the absence of specific PAH types from the various locations under investigation

4.0 Conclusions

The physicochemical characteristics and spatial distribution of various PAH types present in sediments and water samples from the eight (8) different communities located in Delta State have been investigated. The findings confirmed that the pH of the water samples from KOK (5.60), OLO (5.70), and UZE (5.20) locations was acidic. The outcome indicates significant implications for the concentration, mobility, and persistence of contaminants in these water samples. Additionally, the highly acidic pH signifies reduced microbial degradation and enhanced adsorption of contaminants to sediments in these locations (Naz et al., 2022; Aryal, 2024). The findings established that sediment from BAT was most contaminated with PAHs, while sediment from TSE was the least contaminated with PAHs. The findings on the PAH contaminant distribution in the water samples collected across all eight locations under investigation are presented in **Table 3a and 3b**. The result proved that PAH type naphthalene was predominantly absent across 8 locations in water. In contrast, of all the PAH contaminant types under investigation, benzo[b]fluoranthene, although relatively absent in samples collected from OKE and OLO locations, was significantly present in water samples collected from the other 6 locations under investigation. However, the findings from Figure 3 (b) proved that across all 8 locations under investigation, the water sample collected from KOK is the most contaminated with the various PAH types, with a cumulative PAH concentration of 4.51 $\mu\text{g/L}$, and ranking 1st in PAH contamination levels, corresponding to a 16.2% in the percentage PAHs spatial distribution. This was closely followed by UZE with a cumulative PAH concentration of 4.43 $\mu\text{g/L}$ corresponding to approximately 16% of the distribution.

5.0 Recommendations

The Communities studied in this research are associated with PAHs contamination as a result of oil exploration in such areas. PAHs in oil Producing areas can be remediated using Three broad approaches. These include Bio-remediation, Chemical and Physical remediation

- ❖ **Bio-remediation:** can be done through
 - Microbial degradation through the use of bacteria or fungi which can break down PAHs into harmless compounds.
 - Myco-remediation involving the use of enzymes to degrade High Molecular Weight (HMW) PAHs.
 - Phyto-remediation which involve using plants to stimulate microbial degradation of PAHs
- ❖ **Chemical remediation:** This involve the use of reagents to oxidize or transform PAHs processes like advanced Oxidation, (AOPs) processes and chemical surfactant washing can be used
- ❖ **Physical remediation:** This is important when contaminant concentration is very high.
 - Soil excavation and replacement
 - Thermal desorption – heating soil to volatilize and capture PAHs
 - Solid-phase extraction and adsorption- using activated carbon, biochar or nano-materials to adsorb PAHs to adsorb from waste water or soils.

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